

Why is the feasibility study of relativity experiments all blank?

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Why do experiments verifying relativity lack preliminary feasibility studies? The first validation experiment of relativity, the 1919 solar eclipse photography experiment, was there no feasibility study for the experiment plan or principle? The 1971 global atomic clock experiment, in that era, feasibility studies shouldn't have been forgotten, yet they were absent. The 2015 gravitational wave experiment had engineering feasibility studies, but the important feasibility studies for the experimental principle were still missing. All relativity verification experiments collectively lack feasibility studies. Why do relativity experiment projects always deviate from scientific research norms?

I've written an article titled 'A Retrospective Study on the Feasibility of Testing Relativity', where I use a retrospective method to fill in the feasibility study for past relativity experiments. 'A Retrospective Study on the Feasibility of Testing Relativity' is released in two parts to make it easier to translate from Chinese to English. The conclusion of this article is: any experiment using clocks to verify time dilation in relativity cannot pass the feasibility assessment, including the global atomic clock experiments and the atomic clocks in modern GPS systems.

My overall evaluation of the validation experiments for relativity: All experiments based on principles like the 1919 solar eclipse photography (regardless of the precision of the instruments) are hard to justify for feasibility. All experiments that use clocks to verify time dilation, my article has already confirmed cannot pass feasibility justification. The 2015 gravitational wave experiments could have their feasibility justified by the current experimental teams, but the public should be allowed to raise doubts during this process. Therefore, it's expected that the feasibility justification of gravitational wave experiments will be difficult, and the question is whether the research team will accept public judgment.

Public doubts should not be excluded from the scientific system, for example, Dr A.G. Kelly and my own doubts about the around-the-world atomic clock experiments are completely correct.

The articles I have written questioning the experiments include:

'Error Analysis On Around-The-World Atomic Clocks Experiments⑦',

'Error Analysis On Around-The-World Atomic Clocks Experiments⑨',

'Retrospective Study on the Feasibility of Relativity Verification'. My articles analyse whether the experimental plans are feasible and

judge if the experimental data is authentic based on the principles of physics, achieving success. The data in Dr A.G. Kelly's article 'Hafele & Keating Tests; Did They Prove Anything?' provides direct evidence for my articles, and my articles are a correct application

of basic physics principles in relativity verification experiments, fully capable of serving as a standard for evaluating the feasibility of around-the-world atomic clock experiments.

To this end, I applied for part-time positions at universities or research institutions, becoming the first advocate for testing the feasibility of relativity experiments and the earliest formulator of standards for evaluating their feasibility.

Dr A.G. Kelly's bibliographic reference:

Kelly, A. G. Hafele and Keating Tests: Did They Prove Anything? Simultaneously published in Galilean Electrodynamics, Vol.11 (2000) and Physics Essays, 13(4), Dec 2000.

Dr A.G. Kelly's article link:

<https://www.cartesio-episteme.net/h&kpaper.htm>

The original data of the global atomic clock cited in Dr A.G. Kelly's article were obtained by the author from the US Navy observation station under the US Freedom of Information Act.

My articles

"Error Analysis On Around-The-World Atomic Clocks Experiments⑦"

"Error Analysis On Around-The-World Atomic Clocks Experiments⑨"

Links are as follows:

<https://vixra.org/abs/2602.0138>

<https://zenodo.org/records/19758819>

<https://zenodo.org/records/20484821>

Articles pending translation from Chinese to English:

"Feasibility Retrospective Study on the Verification of Relativity"

"Discussion on the Theoretical Structure of Relativity"

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